

Power Grid Data Quality Filter and Machine Learning for Event Classification

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Abstract

The stability and reliability of the power grid are of great importance to the economy and national security. The power grid is a complex system that has many interconnected networks. With the advent of phasor measurement unit (PMU) data, system operators can for the first time view the status of the power systems from a wide area interconnection level. Since there are constant disturbances happening in the power grid, data analytics techniques could be valuable for applications on PMU data that inform the operators regarding significant or interesting power system events. In this study, we develop a data processing and machine learning approach that handles streaming PMU data for detecting and classifying power system events. This paper provides details regarding the techniques we use for filtering out common PMU data quality issues. Also presented is a machine learning classifier that can distinguish between generator trips and other type of power system events. Among the other type of power system events, we also develop metrics based on k-means clustering for the characterization of such events in order to discover interesting ones. Testing conducted on real world PMU data shows that the approach achieves satisfactory results.

Key Words: PMU, Data Quality, Machine Learning, Event Classification

1. Introduction

Power systems are interconnected networks that experience disturbances constantly. It is important to coordinate among system operators for mitigating disturbances, especially the ones that affect the whole interconnection. Phasor measurement unit (PMU) data are hence significant because they provide a wide area view of power systems that is otherwise unavailable. PMUs stream measurements at a high rate, typically 30 or 60 times per second. Each measurement is time stamped to a common clock using the global positioning system (GPS) satellites. The Eastern Interconnection Situational Awareness and Monitoring System (ESAMS) was developed by Electric Power Group (EPG) and the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) with leadership from Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL) to help operators to share insightful information among operating entities (Follum et al., 2020). Part of ESAMS is the machine learning application to detect and classify power system events.

Before the development of the machine learning application in ESAMS, an atypicality engine was developed by the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) which applies statistical methods to PMU data to identify anomalous behavior that can go undetected by human operators. After applying this atypicality engine on several month of real-world PMU data, it became apparent that most of the events flagged by it were in fact attributable to data quality issues that persisted beyond the checks implemented within ESAMS or

common events that were not of much interest to system operators. Therefore, the purpose of the research detailed in this paper is to identify persistent data quality signatures as well as what we are labelling as “common” events in order to distinguish events that are not due to data quality issues and are interesting to operators. Data quality filters are implemented to discard false events due to data quality issues and machine learning methods are developed to provide additional information about the type of commonly detected events and highlight truly anomalous grid behaviors.

2. Data

We studied five months of Eastern Interconnection PMU data from the anonymized FOA 1861 dataset (Banning et al., 2013). The data are stored in matrix format with PMU channels representing the columns and time records making up the rows. The data contain frequency (FR) and voltage angle (VA) channels for a select number of PMUs at 30 Hz, resulting in 1,800 records per minute of data. Additionally, a subset of possible PMU pairs was selected and the phase angle difference was computed for each pair creating additional phase angle difference channels (PAD). The dataset usually contains around 20 channels of time series depending on the quality of the data.

3. Methods

The pre-processing and filtering algorithms as well as the following modules in ESAMS are all applied on a minute-by-minute basis. Within the ESAMS program, the data quality filter will first be utilized to ensure the data passing through the following algorithms are without data quality issues and in a tidy format. After the data quality filter, the atypicality engine will screen through the minutes to calculate an atypicality score for each minute of the data. This part flags the atypical minutes. Afterwards, a machine learning classifier that aims at detecting generator trips will be applied to the atypical minutes. For the atypical minutes that do not come from a generator trip, we develop metrics to characterize them in order to discover more interesting events. We discuss each part of the process in details in this section.

3.1 Data Quality Filter

During an initial ESAMS demonstration period, it became apparent that most of the events flagged by the atypicality engine were attributable to either common grid events, such as line switching and generator trips, or data quality issues that were not flagged by ESAMS before being passed to the atypicality engine. Thus, a data quality filter with additional checks to flag poor-quality data missed by the data management software in ESAMS was developed. The atypicality engine analyzes PADs, which are the difference between two voltage angles measured in different parts of the system, for atypical behaviors. The PAD channels are the primary input to the atypicality engine. The goal of all data quality filtering is to improve the fidelity of the atypicality results through reliable PAD channel data.

The engine also has access to measurements of frequency that can be used for data quality checks and event classification. The data quality check for voltage angle measurements requires a set of frequency measurements that are mostly reliable. Thus, two simple data quality checks were applied to frequency measurements, even though they are not directly analyzed by the atypicality engine. The first check simply discards any values in the frequency channels that are below 59 Hz or above 61 Hz. Next, the standard deviation of each frequency channel is computed. Any channels with a standard deviation of zero imply that the signal is locked, and all values are discarded. In addition, a threshold for

consecutive identical values is used to handle cases where the frequency is locked for less than a full minute. One challenge in setting this threshold is that frequency signals produced by PMUs are commonly quantized to discrete values, and these quantized signals can have several identical values in a row that are valid measurements. The goal is to select a threshold that retains quantized frequency measurements while discarding signals that are truly locked.

Voltage angle channels can also be locked but typically for much shorter periods than frequency channels. Such data also often contain missing data before and after the locked portions. Calculating a PAD signal using one normal voltage angle channel and one voltage angle channel suffering from this particular issue results in false spikes in the PAD channel, which can undesirably trigger the atypicality detector.

The next filter is based on a comparison between a trusted reference frequency measurement and the frequency derived from each PMU's voltage angle (Zhang et al., 2013). If the derived frequency does not match the reference frequency, it indicates that the underlying voltage angle is suspicious. For comparison with the median of all reliable frequency measurements (F_{ref}), a derived frequency (F_{deriv}) was calculated as the scaled second order difference of each PMU's voltage angle measurement. Each RMSE between F_{ref} and F_{deriv} is compared against a threshold to determine if the underlying voltage angle should be flagged for probable data quality issues. If this RMSE exceeds the threshold, then the voltage angle from the PMU, along with any PAD values calculated from it, are discarded.

Each of the data quality filters discussed to this point are run independently and aggregated in a single flag storage container. The next filter discards one additional data point on either side of existing flags in the flag storage container, as these often prove to be unreliable data. Implementing all filters to this point can result in very little reliable data remaining. To avoid an adverse impact on the reliability of the atypicality results, the final data quality filter discards an entire channel if more than 50 percent of all data points in the flag storage container are flagged.

3.2 Atypicality Engine

The atypicality score was created by Amidan and Ferryman (Amidan et al., 2005). It is originally developed to flag atypical patterns in the airline industry. This score is based on time series feature extraction, clustering, principal component analysis, and statistical distributions. After applying the atypicality engine for a short period of time, a baseline can be established and a threshold will be determined. Any minutes that exceeds the threshold will be flagged as 'atypical'.

3.3 Event Classification

One of the power grid events that is of particular interest to system operators is a generator tripping offline. Therefore, the event classification task has two stages. The first stage is the classification of atypical events into either generator trips or other types of events. This part is done using a machine learning event classifier based on gradient boosting machines (GBM) (Follum et al., 2020). The second stage is for the other type of events; event metrics are developed to characterize these events. There are six metrics for each event, three from the PAD channels and three from the frequency channels. With each metric for one event, also calculated is the percentile of the metric compared to historical events, showing how significant the event is considering historically recorded metrics.

3.3.1 Machine Learning Classifier

Among the several conventional machine learning algorithms, GBM was chosen based on the classification performance. Boosting is an ensemble machine learning method (Friedman, 2001). The main idea of boosting is to combine “weak learners” into a “strong learner”. Strong learners often have higher prediction accuracy compared to weak learners. The weak learners being boosted by this method can be any machine learning classifiers. The decision tree technique is a common choice, and it is the choice of this study.

By applying the gradient boosting machine technique to data passed through the large angle voltage difference filter, a model can learn to distinguish between events labeled as generator trips and other power system events. This data must be distilled into several features that the model can be trained on. The features used are the 16 signatures used in the previous anomaly detection component (Amidan et al., 2018), as well as 6 frequency multi-channel features and 6 PAD multi-channel features added in (Follum et al., 2020). During the model training process, historical events were used to train the GBM model. Repeated cross validation has been applied to fine-tune the hyper-parameters of GBM to avoid over-fitting.

3.3.2 Event Metrics

The detailed metric calculations for the other type of events are described in this section.

- **Angle difference sudden changes (AD_SC)** The first order difference of the PAD channels is calculated and a k -means clustering algorithm is performed on the resulting differences with $k = 2$ and with 100 random starting points. The best clustering result is determined by using the silhouette values (Shahapure et al., 2020). Once the best clustering is found, the mean silhouette value for this clustering is used as the metric. This metric measures whether there are sudden changes in the angle difference channels. The calculation is done for all the PAD channels that pass the data quality filter and the maximum of the metrics is recorded as the final metric. Therefore, if there is at least one channel with sudden changes behavior, this event will be classified as having angle difference sudden changes. The approach of taking the maximum across channels is utilized for the rest of the metrics as well.
- **Frequency sudden changes (FR_SC)** This is the same calculation as described above but for the frequency channel, which characterizes the sudden changes in the frequency channels.
- **Angle difference sudden changes 3 groups (AD_SC_3)** This is a similar metric as the AD_SC but when conducting the k -means clustering, we set $k = 3$. This metric is complementary to AD_SC because for some sudden changes, the changes happen in both directions, hence a 3-means clustering fits the first order difference better and can better flag such events.
- **Frequency sudden changes 3 groups (FR_SC_3)** This is the same calculation as described above but for the frequency channel.
- **Angle difference shift (AD_shift)** A k -means clustering algorithm is performed on the time domain PMU data with $k = 2$ and with 100 random starting points. The best clustering result is determined by using the silhouette values. Once the best clustering is found, the mean silhouette value for this clustering is used as the metric. This metric measures whether there are two distinct groups in the angle difference channels, meaning the angle difference shifts to another level during the event.

- **Frequency shift (FR_shift)** This is the same calculation as described above but for the frequency channel.

4. Results

4.1 Data Quality Filter

An example of the locked voltage angle channels is provided in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows an example of PAD signal calculation suffering from the locked voltage angle channel and resulting in false spikes.

Figure 1: Bad data example

Figure 2: False spike example

The improvements from the upgrades in Section 3.1 were evident when comparing atypical engine results from before and after their implementation. For example, we reviewed results from a three-hour window and found that six atypical periods were initially identified. All exhibited data quality problems described in Section 3.1. After implementing the upgraded data quality checks, two atypical periods were identified in the window, and both corresponded to actual events. Of all the events identified in the 5 months of data, only a handful of them appeared to be due to data quality issues. This is a dramatic improvement over earlier results, including those from the ESAMS demonstration, where a significant portion of atypical periods were due to data quality problems.

4.2 Event Classification

During the GBM training, the hyper-parameter tuning process was able to find a model that works perfectly for both the training and testing data, as can be seen by Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: GBM training results

		Truth	
		Gen	Other
Prediction	Event Type		
	Gen	59	0
	Other	0	61

Table 2: GBM testing results

		Truth	
		Gen	Other
Prediction	Event Type		
	Gen	15	0
	Other	0	16

The detected and classified event examples are shown in this section. The first event example in Figure 3 is a generator tripping event classified by the GBM classifier. The sudden drop in frequency is a typical pattern for the generator trips.

Figure 3: Correctly classified generator trip example

The following examples are interesting events indicated by the new metrics for the other type of events. As mentioned before, among the other type of events, the atypicality engine sometime flags events that are uninteresting, meaning within the time domain there is no obvious change or pattern for any channels. The new metrics help to identify more interesting events, for example the sudden changes and shifting among the PAD or frequency channels, which can be seen in the examples here.

Figure 4 is an example with AD_SC_3 metric of 0.961, where sudden changes happening in both directions can be seen.

Figure 4: AD_SC_3 example

Figure 5 is an example with the FR_SC metric being 0.565.

Figure 5: FR_SC example

5. Conclusions

In this study we developed statistical and machine learning methods to filter out common data quality issues and classify and characterize power system events using the PMU data from real-world power grid. The testing results show that the proposed approach filters out all the commonly seen data quality issues, the generator trip classifier is able to distinguish between generator trips and other types of events, and the metrics for the other types of events help to identify more interesting events. Moreover, the data quality filter developed in this study will be used to populate a data quality section of the Grid Event Signature Library (GESL) (ORNL, LLNL, 2023).

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